

**Key changes in the Marketing environment to identify
growth opportunities for BMW**

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Introduction

The history of the BMW Corporation, penned by innovators, trailblazers, and talented designers, is just as fascinating as its goods and innovations. The BMW Group is now the world's top producer of luxury cars and motorcycles and a significant supplier of luxury financial and mobility services. It has over 30 manufacturing and assembly sites and a global sales network. To provide additional ways to guarantee development and success, this report will examine the dynamic macro and microenvironmental dynamics that may help the organization identify its growth plans using the PESTEL framework, Porter's five forces, and SWOT framework. **(BMW Group)**

Environmental Analysis (Macro and Micro)

PESTLE Analysis

The PESTLE analysis is the most effective tool for analyzing company external factors including company potential opportunity and threat. In Appendix 1 show the pestle analysis for the BMW company of the UK, and three biggest elements describe below:

Political Factors: After leaving Brexit, the UK faces lots of obstacles in the imports section, and it has an effect on BMW business. For the reason BMW supply chain is disrupted and BMW profit growth fell down and BMW increased their car price. After leaving Brexit, UK unemployment increased and it is 4.2%, which is high since 1974. BMW moved some engine production from the UK to Africa due to leaving Brexit. Overall, for political factors BMW faces lots of difficult situations and effects on their business. **(Statista, The Irish time, Automotive Europe news)**

Technological Factors: BMW has launched reach now services, and there are three options, Consumer use it by apps and majority options can be controlled by reach now services. Already BMW has made a partnership with Alexa for their customer and new innovation for adding technology in BMW vehicles. All consumers take advantages to control, control music, and control some home device by using Alexa. BMW has launched their My BMW app, and people can start a vehicle by pressing a key through the Mobile App. For using high technology, Customers want to buy a car, and it will help to increase their price strategy. **(Intel, WGSN, BMW UK)**

Ecological Factors: BMW make electric power up car for minimizes use fuel, because it reduces CO2 in the environment. Besides this BMW work with manage ecological all resources, and they adopt recycling technologies, like as BMW use 100% secondary materials for reduce materials west in environment. BMW work develop circular economy. In the UK, BMW keep biggest impact by working with Circular economy. BMW industry already use Combustion engines for reduce CO2 in environment. BMW is committed to work for environment for develop sustainability. **(BMW UK, BMW group)**

Porter Five Forces

Porters five forces analysis is one of the best analyses to company strategic understand and it will help to make company more profitable. In Appendix 2.1, show the five porters of the UK, Automotive industry BMW. Two of high elements, shaw below:

Competitive Rivalry: BMW market is board; their competitive rival is two types direct and indirect. BMW biggest rival, Audi, Mercedes, Tesla, Volvo etc. some of direct rival and some of indirect rival. Like as, Audi is direct rival for BMW and Volvo is indirect rival for BMW. Now BMW developing research for use high technology, and BMW already launched electric vehicle but ford already invest 20 billion for sales outcome in 2030. **(Mathilde carlier, Statista,2023)**

1 (1)	BMW
2 (2)	Audi
3 (3)	Mercedes-Benz
4 (4)	Volkswagen
5 (6)	Toyota
6 (7)	Hyundai
7 (14)	Volvo
8 (5)	Honda
9 (8)	Seat
10 (12)	Mitsubishi

Figure 1: BMW competitor in the UK

(Global data 2023)

Bargaining power of Customer: Customers rely on reviews from periodicals, websites, and other sources today. Reviews provide a wealth of automobile data, including comparisons among cars in the same segment. This information is precious to customers regarding pricing, features, and models. Such details significantly influence customers' purchasing decisions, and most rely on these reviews. (Anon,n.d, 2015). Increased competition has additionally bolstered customers' bargaining power. Each brand strives to increase its consumer base and market share. Most prominent brands, including BMW's closest competitors, invest substantially in advertising and development activities. (Pratap, A, 2019)

Competitors Capability analysis:

Through the measure of competitors capability analysis, help to understand what is your strength, weakness, and what their marketing strategy, pricing strategy, what their new innovation, goals, vision, and it will be helpful to make your business plan easy. In appendix 2.2 show the UK automotive company competitor's capability analysis between the BMW and Audi. In this analysis show the company competitor's same product, strategy, market share, technological advance and social media presence. Product range of BMW and Audi, SAVS for BMW and Sportback for Audi, and Sedans and Salon are the competitors of products, and market share 9.78% share was the peak market share of BMW (Statista,2022) and 3.1 % and 9.8% for Audi market share. (Statista, 2023), however, BMW is the market leading position than Audi, But Audi and Mercedes Banz are the biggest rival for BMW.

Situation Analysis (SWOT):

Through the analysis of SWOT, it can measure company strength, weakness, opportunity, and threats, and make plan for better business. It is easily measure what is the best recommendation and it will be the best for company future. In appendix 3 show SWOT analysis of BMW. According to analysis, company have financial threat and company opportunity, like as, using high advance technology, and it attract customer to buy car. Also, company weakness, like as high debt, it is concern sign for BMW company. For all of this need to measure SOWT analysis and take appropriate action and advantages to move forward company.

Recommendation;

Weakness into strength: BMW reveal some weakness, but it has alternative to perform against this weakness. Van and truck segments BMW automotive market portfolio is weaker, but electric vehicle have advance technology it will increase sell and increased revenue, as a result debt will be increased and it will be helpful to grant loan and it use for product development.

Threats into opportunity: Majority threats creates for environmental, like as external. Like as Russia and Ukraine war, increased petroleum prices and decrease sales, and high competition in automotive market. To convert threats in to opportunity, two growth opportunity are described below:

Growth opportunity 1:

By developing electric vehicle, and make it trend to and make it UK customer segment base and performance is affordable. Company should invest on charging section to increased battery health for make better performance, it will increase sustainability and reduce the threats and product portfolio reduce competition.

Growth Opportunity 2:

The cars' digitalization and connection features may expand BMW's growth prospects in the United Kingdom. Creating automobiles with cutting-edge features like voice control, navigation, and connectivity to smartphones and other devices can improve user experiences. Creating fully and semi-autonomous driving capabilities and forming alliances with developing nations like China can also help them find high-quality spare parts, equipment, technology solutions and less disruption from suppliers. Gaining more consumers unwilling to spend money on gasoline will lessen the danger of competition, and working with developing nations can result in more cost-effective solutions.

Conclusion:

The study mentioned above shows that BMW faces risks from political, technical, and environmental factors in the UK. In the UK market, it is characterized by fierce competition and the possibility of customer bargaining. The Audi Group, its main rival, has a more extensive product line and a larger market share. Sustainability, digitalization, and connection are its two growth prospects in creating electric vehicles, which will help it compete in the United Kingdom's market and turn its risks into opportunities.

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Appendices:

Task 1: Audit Research

Appendix 1: Macro-Environment (Pestle analysis of BMW company)

	External/Internal factor to consider	Opportunity or Threat	Ranking
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> leaving Brexit, the UK faced lots of challenges in imports, and UK economic growth fell; that's why it increased BMW car prices. (Satista,3154) 	Threat	4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Due to leave from Brexit, The UK unemployment rate is 4.2%, it is high since 1974. It keeps impact on BMW business (Satista,36274) 	Threat	3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BMW has needed to transfer some engines from the UK to South Africa due to leaving Brexit. (The Irish Time) 	Threat	2
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Due to leave Brexit, generate to uncertain future of the UK automotive industry. (GHarle, 2019) 	Opportunity	4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UK importers have warned of serious collapse to supply chain due to leave Brexit. (Automotive News Europe. 2020) 	Threat	3
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Covid-19 and exit from Brexit total goods trades decreased 23.1% by Europe 	Threat	3

	<p>(national statistics, 2021)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMW announced they make new plant for manufacturing new electric mini car, after funding £600 million by UK government. (The Independent, 2023) • BMW already launched Electric car in the UK market. By released this, their sales are increase, because of their new car mobility and it's fully automotive. (Statista, 2023) • For leave Brexit, and covid 19 massive supply chain disrupted. (Tetley, L 2022) • Due to leave from Brexit, new border rule increases the car price such as mini car. (BBC, 2018) 	<p>Opportunity</p> <p>Opportunity</p> <p>Threat</p> <p>Threat</p>	<p>4</p> <p>3</p> <p>3</p> <p>3</p>
<p>Social</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMW use combustion engines, it usually for climate protection. combustion engines is reduced CO₂ and reduce smoke emissions as well. It is very positive things for human society. (BMW group, 2023) • BMW goals for their consumer is make sure safe journey and sustainability. (Shaw, A.A, 2020) • BMW committed to build an educated 	<p>Opportunity</p> <p>Opportunity</p>	<p>4</p> <p>3</p>

	<p>community for sustainable development and build better future for children. (Miller, K, 2022)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For safety features, increasing demand and it chance to expand Business. (crowjack.com) • BMW take customer service feedback from twitter by customer and give comments reply. (swotandpestleanalysis.com) 	<p>Opportunity</p> <p>Opportunity</p> <p>Opportunity</p>	<p>2</p> <p>3</p> <p>2</p>
<p>Technological</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMW launched reach now services. It gives consumer extra advantages. (Mintel) • BMW make styleGAN over the 50,000 images from across 900 years. And they selected 50 visual artists for previous collabs, and this art design BMW 8 series frieze. (WGSN) • BMW make partnership with Alexa for control in board for their mobile application in car. (Mintel 2017) • Intuitional operation using by voice commands. (BMW UK) 	<p>Opportunity</p> <p>Opportunity</p> <p>Opportunity</p> <p>Opportunity</p>	<p>3</p> <p>2</p> <p>3</p> <p>2</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start vehicle without press key by pressing button in phone. (BMW UK) 	Opportunity	1
Legal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company needs to give focus their labour section, that need to make sure their labour law maintains standard quality for the further sustainability. (BMW group) 	Threat	3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company use harmful chemical, taxonomy. As a result, it is a concern for future BMW company sustainability. (Financial Time, Hancock, A,2023) 	Threat	4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BMW use huge number of Technology, that's why, they make copyright and patent, but every country has different law, as a result it's amended by various country (Shaw, A.A. (2020)) 	Threat	3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100 customers complain for engine fail issue. (Shaw, A.A. (2020)) 	Threat	4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 90 customers complain, sudden fire in their park BMW car. (Zigu (2020)) 	Threat	4
Ecological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BMW make Electric power up car and minimizes to use fuel. As a result, it reduces CO2 in the environment. (Miller, J. (2020)) 	Opportunity	4

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMW focus on environment protection and BMW work with manage ecological resources. (bmw uk) 	Opportunity	4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMW working with development circular economy. (bmw uk) 	Opportunity	2
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMW aware to protect natural finite resources. (bmwgroup) 	Opportunity	2
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For reduce wasting raw materials, BMW use 100% secondary raw materials. (bmwgroup) 	Opportunity	3

Appendix 2:

External Micro-Environment Analysis (Porter's 5 Forces & Competitor Capability Analysis)

2.1 Porters 5 Forces- BMW

Elements	Factors to Consider
Competitive Rivalry	<p>High</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are lots of BMW Competitive rival, such as Audi, Mercedes, Tesla, Volvo, etc and direct competitors is Mercedes and indirect competitors is Volvo. (Team, MS, 2022) • BMW sales 2.4 million vehicle, on the other hand Volkswagen sales 1.61 million vehicle in 2021 under the Audi. (Mathilde carlier,2023) • Toyota motor company sold almost 9 million vehicles in 2022 (Mathilde carlier,2023) • Ford contemplate to invest more than 20 billion U, S dollar for electric vehicle entirely 2025 and this plan for 40 to 50 per cent sales come from 2030. (Mathilde carlier,2023)
Threats of New Entrants	<p>Low</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are lots of company already lead in automotive industry, and they already reserve global market, so, there is few chances to new entrance and make better business. (Team, MS, 2023) • There needs high capital investment, and need skilled human resources. So, there are few chances to exit and entry in automotive industry. (Team, MS, 2023)
Threats of substitutes	<p>Medium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The automobile industry is switching to electricity; in 2021, Tesla, a multinational company based in America, held the largest market share at 14%. BMW held a 4.82% marketplace position in plugin electric cars. (Statista, 2021)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The business's capacity to garner a niche market is attributed to the product division for luxury cars, automobiles, and sports cars; therefore, any replacement must be done with the loss of brand loyalty. (Statista,2021)
Bargaining Power of Suppliers	<p>Medium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The fact that the vast majority of the goods and services offered by the number of vendors are not distinctive further diminishes the bargaining power of BMW suppliers. (BMW group reports,2016) To maintain an association with the company, suppliers must adhere to their rules of conduct and accept business conditions organization. (Team, MS, 2023)
Bargaining Power of Customers	<p>High</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customers rely on reviews from periodicals, websites, and other sources today. Reviews provide a wealth of automobile data, including comparisons among cars in the same segment. This information is precious to customers regarding pricing, features, and models. Such details significantly influence customers' purchasing decisions, and most rely on these reviews. (Anon,n.d, 2015) Increased competition has additionally bolstered customers' bargaining power. Each brand strives to increase its consumer base and market share. Most prominent brands, including BMW's closest competitors, invest substantially in advertising and development activities. (Pratap, A, 2019)

2.2 Competitor Capability Analysis- BMW

Criteria	BMW	Audi
Product Range	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SAVS (X1 sports, X2 coupe SUV, X3, sports utility, X4 sports, X5 sports, X5M, X6) • Sedans (Three series, four series, Five series, seven series, eight series, M3, M8, i4) • Convertible (4 series, 8 series, M4, M8, Z4) <p>(BMW USA, 2019)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sportback (A1, A1 TFSI e, S3) • Salon (A3, S3, RS3, A4, A6, S6,) • Sportback (A7, A7 TFSI e, S7, RS7, Q3, Q3 TFSI e) <p>(AUDI, UK)</p>
Market share	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9.78% was the peak market share of BMW IN 2021. (Statista, 2022) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistently managing a sizable portion of the UK automotive market, the company's market share fluctuated between 3.1% and 9.8%. (Statista, 2023)
Social Media presence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, Tiktok. (Unmetric, 2019) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube. (Unmetric, 2019)
Pricing Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One potential method to value pricing is to ensure the quality of products. • Price differentiation based to vehicle sizes, designs, and variations of automotive. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The business's provision of premium products in Audi dealerships facilitates customers' access to the product line. • Audi Financing offers an innovative financing choice

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prestige pricing strategy whereby prices are determined higher than actual expenses the opinion of customers. 	for the purchase of its products by customers.
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Appendix 3: Internal Micro-Environment Analysis (SWOT Analysis for BMW)

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An intimidating company image. Brand value is 46.33 per cent. (Statista, 2022) • The brand's basic approach is to produce visually appealing and fuel-efficient cars. (Edrawsoft, 2021) • BMW gross profit earning before tax and interest in 2021, 13,999 million euro. (Statista, 2018, b) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conversely, over the past five decades, its debt-to-equity ratio has fallen from 175.8% to 114%. (Pratap, A, 2022) • In the Van and Truck segments, BMW's automotive market portfolio is weaker than that of its competitors (BMW Press group, 2023). • High cost
Opportunity	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automobiles in the future will be driverless. (San Francisco, 2020) • Since environmental friendliness is the norm of the future, any automaker with decades of expertise in hybrid and fully electric vehicles has a significant competitive edge. (Berman, b, 2018) • A reduction in vehicle taxation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several well-known automakers compete fiercely with BMW, including Audi, Mercedes Benz, Porsche, Lexus, and others. (BMW 2022) • Supply chain disrupts due to leave Brexit, and war between Ukraine and Russia. • The war between Russia and Ukraine has pushed up oil prices (Investors in the United Kingdom, 2023)

policies has the potential to boost buyer interest in automotive (Consumer Reports, 2022) .	
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